

**Definite
CCRI**

DEFINITE-CCRI

Data Management Plan

(Final version of Deliverable 1.5)

**Funded by
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Executive Summary

This report, titled Deliverable 1.5, is the final version of the Data Management Plan. It outlines how data is handled during and after the project's lifetime; it includes updates on the type of data that have been handled so far, as well as on the process adopted to receive circular economy project applications.

The document discloses the data collection, sharing, and storing processes, as suggested in the Horizon 2020 Guidelines on data management. The document describes how the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium ensured data security and personal data protection.

In addition, the report describes how data collected, processed and generated comply with the Horizon Europe FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, re-usability).

DEFINITE Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
	Circle Economy	Non-governmental organisation	The Netherlands
	Stad Gent	Municipality	Belgium
	Bankers without Boundaries (BWB)	Non-governmental organisation	Ireland
	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	University	Greece

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List of abbreviations used

- CCRI Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
- EU European Union
- PDA Project Development Assistance
- CSA Coordination and Support Action
- DMP Data Management Plan
- NDA Non Disclosure Agreement

The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell

Effective investment and financing opportunities for circular economy projects in Europe are still few. For securing financing, circular economy projects must meet investors' requirements for bankability and display risk-return profiles to increase investors' trust in impactful projects aimed at advancing the transition to a more circular economy in cities and regions. In order to become less risky and more appealing for investments, projects need to be developed around new and re-designed finance solutions and business models. Transaction costs need to be decreased, and the private finance community needs to be engaged to address legal, administrative and market related challenges. In response to this, the DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a Deal Engine Mechanism, providing technical, financial, and circular economy expertise through local Project Development Assistance (PDA) in an unprecedented and streamlined process to city and regional governments and to project developers. It aims to co-create and prove an end-to-end PDA process, aggregating risk mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the CCRI's service portfolio. This will inject the financial, technical, and managerial know-how into urban circular transitions and ultimately contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Bio-economy Strategy.

DEFINITE-CCRI (*Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – CCRI*) is a Horizon Europe funded project that has started in November 2022.

DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives

The four key objectives at the foundation of the project's vision and work plan are:

- **Objective 1:** To build and operate a deal engine for the CCRI and establish it as a sustainable service offering for cities in Europe.
- **Objective 2:** To close the gap between circular economy projects in cities and regions and investors and finance partners, and to mitigate investment risks for circular economy projects.
- **Objective 3:** To increase the investment viability of innovative, high-impact circularity projects by mitigating risk and increasing their investment readiness.
- **Objective 4:** To successfully launch four investments in circular economy projects up to 20 million Euro investment volume per project in CCRI cities and regions.

1. Introduction

1. Purpose of this document

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an overview of the data management strategy to be applied for data collected, generated, and processed for DEFINITE-CCRI, based on the H2020 Programme Guidelines in FAIR Data Management¹. Based on the current stage of the project it includes some of the data sets that will be further developed during the project lifetime. It provides an overview of the following:

- the type of data to be collected, processed and / or generated;
- methodology, standards, and storage to be applied;
- means for data curation and preservation (including after the end of the project)
- whether data will be shared/made open access;

The plan is meant to provide detailed information on the informed consent procedures that will be implemented regarding collection, storage and protection of personal and sensitive data that might be collected in the activities engaging different stakeholder groups (financiers, cities and regions practitioners, project owners, etc.). The plan will take into consideration different methods and purposes used for data collection and will guide partners to ensure legal compliance. The DMP is a living document in which further information will be made available, based on the development of the Deal Engine Mechanism.

DEFINITE-CCRI aims to provide Project Development Assistance (PDA) consisting of technical, financial, and circular economy expertise to cities, regions, and project owners to develop local bankable projects. The Project Development Assistance services included in the Deal Engine Mechanism are being established and proved during the project lifetime and will be fully digitalised and operated beyond the project lifetime as a self-sustaining portal. The web portal dedicated to operationalising and providing the services is also meant to connect different stakeholders – i.e., project owners, CCRI cities, financial institutions - interested in advancing local circular solutions.

Before focusing on the details of the Deal Engine mechanism, one reflection is needed on timing of data handling. On the one hand, DEFINITE-CCRI processes and generates data internally during the project (WP 2, 3, 4, 5), and the consortium or the entity that is the responsible owner of the data for the data manages and protect them as foreseen in paragraph 1.8 below. On the other hand, data will be collected and managed through a web portal for the Deal Engine mechanism

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

developed and hosted by ICLEI with the aim to allow project applications to specific targeted investors. The web portal will include features such as newsletters, document submissions and data access for relevant stakeholders. Though in the first version of D1.2 the launching date was June 2024, considering that the portal is strongly connected with its business model included in the spin off plan (due in M30), the consortium decided to develop the web portal at a later stage. The application process consisted in a template shared via email and through a google form (see below). Additional details on infrastructure, technicalities, type of data processed, and storage system will be provided in the spin-off plan.

The data sets generated during the project will mirror the approach implemented to develop the Deal Engine Mechanism, as explained below:

1. **Technical and Impact Potential Assessment:** During the first six months of the project, cities and local project owners submitted their project outlines to the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline via email sent to contact@definite-ccri.eu or via a google form available [here](#). As part of WP 2 - City and Investor Engagement and Project Selection, all project partners screened each project outline singularly to determine their suitability to advance the European Green Deal in line with the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities, the European Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) and the European bio-economy strategy. As part of WP 2, 9 project outlines were selected to be further evaluated with respect to their Technical and Impact Potential. An analysis framework of qualitative and quantitative indicators has been developed for the perusal in the TIP assessment for each project (WP 4).
2. **Finance and Investment Baseline Assessment:** DEFINITE-CCRI consortium engages and formalises partnerships with financiers and investors to identify their bankability requirements and drive project development toward meeting their requirements. Upon agreement with the project owners, financiers are provided with generic information on the project ideas, to identify financial instruments suitable for the projects in the pipeline. An analysis framework of qualitative and quantitative indicators has been developed based on the requirements collected from financial institutions partnering with DEFINITE-CCRI; project outlines submitted to the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline have been screened and evaluated based on an analysis framework of qualitative and quantitative indicators has for the perusal in the FIB assessment (WP3, WP2). Based on the assessment outcome, each local project owner receives feedback to adjust their project outline and meet investors' requirements (WP2, WP3, and WP4).
3. **Due Diligence Support:** Based on the TIP and FIB assessments, starting from M18, project owners received due diligence support (WP 3 and WP4), therefore, they were be assisted

in preparing all necessary documents and information input required to improve their investment proposal and submit a finance or investment proposal application to suitable investors collaborating with DEFINITE-CCRI. The type of support provided encompassed technical, legal, and financial development assistance. For each project, we developed a risk profile to minimise all relevant types of project risks. In addition, the realisation of a community of practice (WP6) is providing additional assistance, through the engagement of local experts that will support project owners in overcoming capacity shortages, particularly related to data and information gathering required for robust project development.

4. Based on the completed investment proposal and risk profile established for each selected project, the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium organised two project appraisal events inviting finance and investment partners of DEFINITE-CCRI, and project stakeholders as identified by the local project owner to support each project owner in fulfilling investors' requirements and get their interest in investing in the project. Project appraisal supported project owners to prepare formal submissions to the investment partner (WP 5). All projects approved by DEFINITE-CCRI will be submitted to suitable investors to take up contracting negotiations and formalities for deal brokerage (WP5). The DEFINITE-CCRI consortium partners will continue to follow up with both sides, project owners and investors to facilitate any final steps toward the conclusion of investment contracts.
5. In order to receive additional project outlines, i.e. to validate and to form the basis for continued activities beyond the project lifetime, the consortium has launched a second open call in January 2025, lasting until 23rd of February. Interested parties are asked to submit project related information via a google form (see form [here](#)). The handling of the data is in line with the previous call for project outlines and meets all necessary requirements.

As part of WP 6 (Communication, Replication and Exploitation), the project Consortium developed a **project website** for dissemination and communication activities and will develop a **portal as sub-section** of the website to operate the Deal Engine beyond the project lifetime and allow projects applications, as well as host the evaluation tool and related capacity building materials. Along the course of the project, outcomes, learnings, and experiences of each project undergoing the process are being documented and disseminated via the project website and social media channels and are being utilised in capacity building activities for cities and regions (WP6). Sensitive project outputs are not published on the website. For what concerns the outputs that are expected to be publicly available, we take all the necessary cautions to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation, and sensitive data are aggregated and anonymised before being made

publicly available, when required. Visitors to the project website can contact us at contact@definite-ccri.eu, [Twitter](#), or [LinkedIn](#) and can subscribe to the newsletter, directly linked to the Sendinblue platform². ICLEI EURO is the responsible entity of the Sendinblue account. Further information personal data protection policies of ICLEI EURO and Sendinblue is provided in paragraph 1.8.

² Sendinblue platform, accessible at

https://www.sendinblue.com/?utm_source=adwords_brand&utm_medium=lastclick&utm_content=SendinBlue&utm_extension&utm_term=sendinblue&utm_matchtype=e&utm_campaign=629584539&utm_network=g&km_adid=355470526782&km_adposition&km_device=c&utm_adgroupid=35175414900&gclid=CjwKCAjwI6OiBhA2EiwAuUwWZeKzZSZtltVrmSu2EzeOPrTLBpMgRV2DOPzIQAZTnh4Eyu-BCfUKOhoC33oQAvD_BwE

2. Data Summary

The development of the Deal Engine mechanism relies on the data collected from various sources that allow us to provide local project owners with technical and financial assistance to improve their projects and reach investors requirements. The consortium will collect and generate data to prove the Project Development Assistance methodology implemented and ensure the long-term establishment of the Deal Engine portal.

The objectives are defined below:

- To support project owners in improving the technical potential of their projects;
- To support project owners in fulfilling the financial requirements for bankability;
- To provide project owners with technical, financial, and legal assistance to fulfil the due diligence criteria;
- To develop a Deal Engine mechanism as a self-sustaining tool available online.

Based on the data inputs, identified in table 2 below; DEFINITE-CCRI will generate the following type of data during its lifetime:

- Quantitative and qualitative primary data generated within DEFINITE-CCRI. This type of data derives from the interaction with cities, regions and project owners and might relate to personal details (contacts' information), technologies, business models, financial and economic characteristics of their project ideas. Such data relate to findings from responses gathered through interviews, but it can also encompass deliverables produced by partners as a result of applying their expertise or the conclusions drawn from meetings.
- Qualitative and quantitative secondary data deriving from exiting sources and/or from financial institutions in relation to bankability requirements.

3. Purpose of data collection

The datasets should be based on the type of data collected around the development of the Deal Engine, therefore, to meet the objectives required in the project, different data will have to be collected and processed, including minimum personal data (name, surname, contact) and data and information needed to assess the financial and technical indicators to fulfil with investors' requirements.

Data collection took place across different activities:

Table 1 DEFINITE-CCRI data collection activities

WP	Description of activities	Lead
WP 1	DEFINITE-CCRI Project Management Data collection on Consortium members, participants to regular calls and meetings. Meeting minutes and recordings, project, and administrative documents, as well as project deliverables	ICLEI EURO
WP 2	DEFINITE-CCRI City and Investors engagement Data gathered from project owners on projects submitted to the project pipeline as well as from financial institutions to identify suitable offers to support the projects selected for the deal engine (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3).	ICLEI EURO
WP 3	DEFINITE-CCRI Financial and Legal PDA Collected data from local project owners on the financial criteria needed to provide financial due diligence support. (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3)	BWB
WP 4	DEFINITE-CCRI Technological PDA Collection of technology and impact related data from local project owners and their partners on the proposed projects (D4.1, D4.3)	NTUA
WP 5	DEFINITE-CCRI Project Bankability Appraisal Deal Brokerage Collection of potential additional data needed for deal brokerage, to be complemented based on the proceeding with project owners and financial partners.	BWB
WP 6	DEFINITE-CCRI Dissemination and Exploitation Collection of project general information, website contents, polls results, forms, social media posts (LinkedIn and Twitter), newsletters, banners, flyers, one pagers, brochures, posters, presentations, photographs, educational videos, and online and offline event leads. Project deliverables, public results, and publications will be included. Collection of data on financial, legal experts and/or technical consultancies included in the Community of Practice to provide additional support to project owners, information includes personal data of participants; recordings of capacity building activities, list of participants to the Community of Practice meetings and webinars. Recording of Community of Practice meetings and Capacity building webinars.	CE

4. Methods of data collection and protection actions

As mentioned above, the participation of persons in the DEFINITE-CCRI activities is transversal to different activities or actions within the project. The following section outlines the key activities for processing data received from participants and how the DEFINITE-CCRI partners seek to protect their data protection rights.

As a general reference, *'Personal data,'* is identified in the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as the information meant to identify or make a natural person identifiable. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, and an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person. *'Sensitive personal data'* are personal data revealing: racial or ethnic origin; political opinions; religious or philosophical beliefs; trade-union membership; genetic data; biometric data processed solely to identify a human being; health-related data; data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation. These types of sensitive personal data are protected under EU law and can only be processed by organisations if specific safeguards are in place.

DEFINITE-CCRI will only collect, process, or generate only data that are relevant to the activities aimed at allowing project owners to develop bankable projects. Sensitive data (in the form of those mentioned above) are not required for the foreseen activities; however, if such sensitive data should be collected for the purpose of the project, project partners will request formal approval prior to the collection of any sensitive data.

Below are described the main methods for data collection in DEFINITE-CCRI.

- **Primary data collected by direct input via emails, meetings, surveys, and project outlines, workshops, webinars involving project owners, financiers, and other stakeholder groups.**

To be able to provide project owners with the necessary assistance to develop their circular economy project ideas and direct their project outlines towards meeting financial requirements for bankability (T2.1 & T2.2), project owners filled in a project outline template collecting info on personal data (e.g., name, e-mail, organisation, etc.), technical and financial characteristics of their projects. This process ensures their onboarding in the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline. Data have been collected via a word template completed by projects owners and sent via email to contact@definite-ccri.eu or via a google form available [here](#). Project owners applying to DEFINITE-CCRI to receive PDA have been informed and required for their explicit permission to process their personal data. Data processed include full name, email addresses, address, phone number. Data is stored in the DEFINITE-CCRI Microsoft Teams that is a certified repository, compliant with General Data Protection Regulations³. The application form included the following disclaimer:

³ Microsoft Teams compliance with GDPR <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/compliance/regulatory/gdpr>, accessed 14.04.2023

"DEFINITE-CCRI is an EU-funded project assisting the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative in mainstreaming the circular economy in European cities and regions. DEFINITE-CCRI will provide technical, financial, and circular economy expertise through local Project Development Assistance (PDA) to cities, regions, and project developers to help circular economy projects attract investments. Your participation in DEFINITE-CCRI activities is entirely voluntary. You can terminate it at any time. The information you are providing will be anonymised. Data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction procedures will comply with all national and EU-legislation.

DEFINITE-CCRI is not responsible for errors or omissions while filling in this form.

You can preview the information requested in this online form by downloading the [project outline form](#) and the [estimated budget form](#).

If you have any questions, please contact us: contact@definite-ccri.eu."

The overall application process is expected to be digitalized and included in the web portal, terms and conditions, including on data management, will be defined in the spin-off plan. In parallel, identifying the bankability requirements of financial institutions, as well as financial instruments available (T2.4), imply collection of qualitative data collected through emails and meetings and stored in a word and excel format. Such information is needed for the development of qualitative and quantitative indicators for deal brokerage (T3.1). Data collected are stored in word, excel and images formats in Microsoft Teams. As mentioned above, Microsoft Teams is compliant with the General Data Protection Regulations⁴ and therefore, guarantees data protection in terms of individuals' rights to correct or delete their data, or restrict their data processing. Further information on Microsoft Teams compliance with GDPR is disclosed in paragraph 1.8. Only consortium partners access information on Microsoft Teams via individual account login and password. Participants receive explanation of the purpose of the requested information, how and what they are used for, and they are given the option to opt in or out.

DEFINITE-CCRI activities encompass capacity-building webinars that will be recorded and edited into short training videos to be uploaded to the project web website, and stakeholder consultative meetings for the establishment of a community of practice. The processing of personal data collected for these activities will respect to GDPR privacy rules, and personal information will be aggregated and anonymised. DEFINITE-CCRI has designed an informed consent form (in Annex B) to be used when engaging with external stakeholders.

- **Data collected for the assessment of technical and financial indicators (WP2, WP 3, and WP 4)**

⁴ Microsoft Teams compliance with GDPR <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/compliance/regulatory/gdpr>, accessed 14.04.2023

The financial and technical indicators for project development assistance will be tailor-made to the projects in the Deal Engine pipeline; therefore, the criteria will be defined based on proceedings with project owners. Some of the expected data processed imply projects business and financial information, technical details and personal contact information.

- **Data collected in communication and dissemination (e.g., newsletter, social media channels, project website, project web portal)**

DEFINITE-CCRI use different communication channels - website, newsletters, and social media - that collect subscribers' e-mail contacts, data on the number of website visitors, and social media followers (see table below). Communication materials and dissemination activities via the DEFINITE-CCRI website (www.definite-ccri.eu) are meant to redirect stakeholders to the project website providing relevant information on DEFINITE-CCRI. The website has a dedicated contact form and link to other project social networks. Website visitors can directly subscribe to the project newsletter that is also shared on the DEFINITE-CCRI social networks. Any data gathered and shared through the project communication channels will be treated with respect to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

- **Data collected through management and coordination activities**

Other coordination actions include the data collected during the management and coordination actions, e.g., the names and e-mails of the consortium. Data will be stored the form of .pdf, .docx and .xlsx files in the DEFINITE-CCRI MS Teams channel accessible only for project partners via individual account and password.

- **Secondary data: collected via the review of documents, relevant project documents and scientific literature, available online**

The development of technical and financial indicators relies on data collected from scientific data available online.

All Work Package (WP) Leaders are responsible for data management within their work package and as indicated in the table above, are custodians of the data collected and used in the respective WPs.

5. Data Utility

Most of the data collected will be useful for the DEFINITE-CCRI team to provide legal, technical, and financial assistance to project owners, to mitigate risks, improve their technological and impact potential, achieve the due diligence criteria needed to deliver bankable projects. Several personal

data were collected from financiers, project owners, service providers. These were stored in MS Teams and accessible only to the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium required to access the DEFINITE-CCRI Microsoft Teams channel via the institutional account and password. DEFINITE-CCRI aims to contribute to the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative and develop a Project Development Assistance tool meant to deliver bankable circular economy projects, therefore all public deliverables displaying the mechanism, and relevant criteria to be met, are published on the project website. Sensitive information is kept confidential.

6. Formats of the data

During virtual and in-person meetings, interviews, workshops, etc. **qualitative data** are collected through note taking, video and/or audio recording and photos. The data collected during the project are used in the following formats: Text documents (.DOC, .DOCX, .PDF, .ODT); Images (JPG, PNG); Audio (MP3); Video (MP4)

Quantitative data will be stored as .XLS, .XLSX or .CSV files.

Data are stored in the DEFINITE-CCRI MS Teams channel, accessible to project partners via user account and password.

7. Standards and metadata

Data are documented following the common standards provided by in the Grant Agreement:

- The terms “Horizon Europe” or “Euratom funding”
- The name of the action, acronym and the grant number
- Publication date
- The author

The metadata (Information about the data collected, stored, and processed during the project) are summarised for each of the data set identified in the project. This includes information on the type of data, description, access mechanism, format, storage point, who has access, back up responsibility, preservation, access after project, etc. The Annex A below provides detailed information on the project data.

8. Data security

All collected data are stored for the entire duration (two and half years) of the DEFINITE-CCRI project. Project outputs are stored on the Microsoft Teams platform, which is a certified repository accessible via individual username and password and are also available as back-up in the data

owners' institutional servers and hard drivers. Microsoft Teams complies with the General Data Protection Regulations, ensuring individuals the rights, among other, to correct their data, to delete or restrict their data processing. Microsoft Teams ensures the encryption of the data communicated via Teams and stored within its data centres. Only project consortium can access the Teams folders via requested users' authentication⁵.

All project partners are responsible for data being processed within their private servers and will ensure data protection. Partners will ensure that data security controls have been implemented to minimize the risk of information leak and destruction.

For what concerns the long-term conservation and secure storage, DEFINITE-CCRI consortium complies with the General Data Protection Regulations, by storing personal data for the shortest time needed for project delivery. DEFINITE-CCRI established time limits to erase or review the data stored.

For the storage and long-term conservation of dissemination and communication materials (reports, videos, briefs, etc), these are ensured through the project website. The project website and the project cloud will be accessible at least a year after the end of the project, as foreseen in the Grant Agreement.

Sensitive project outputs and data are stored only in the Microsoft Teams platform accessible via individual username and password. Personal data might be stored for a longer period in the interest of developing the Deal Engine web portal, provided that appropriate technical and organisational measures will be put in place (such as anonymisation, encryption, etc.)

2. Ethical aspects and GDPR

DEFINITE-CCRI applies all ethical requirements to the processing of personal data respecting the principles and provisions made under the project Grant Agreement and EU laws on GDPR to ensure fairness, transparency and accountability of the data processing, data quality and confidentiality.

a. Obligations in processing of personal data

Regarding management of personal data and involvement of external stakeholders, DEFINITE-CCRI complies with the following main obligations in processing personal data:

- Data should, wherever possible, are processed in anonymised form.

⁵ Security and Microsoft Teams, <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoftteams/teams-security-guide>, accessed 14.04.2023

- Data processing is subject to free and fully informed consent of the persons concerned (unless already covered by another legal basis, e.g., legitimate or public interest).
- Data processing must NOT be performed in secret and participants must be made aware that they take part in the project.
- Data are be processed ONLY if it is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for DEFINITE-CCRI.

b. Informed consent

Regarding management of personal data and involvement of project participants, DEFINITE-CCRI has designed an informed consent form (in Annex B) to be used when engaging with project stakeholders. Data collected/generated and processed in DEFINITE-CCRI is only needed for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes relative to project's objectives. Moreover, all project partners processing data during DEFINITE-CCRI fully abide with their respective applicable national as well as EU regulations.

c. Data protection in dissemination activities

For dissemination activities, we will use the project website and social media channels. No personal data will be collected via the project website, unless visitors subscribe to the newsletter. The only type of personal data collected through subscription to the newsletters is the e-mail address. ICLEI, as responsible for the website development, added a privacy policy on the website (accessible [here](#)) following transparency principles.

Visitors subscribe to the project newsletter via Sendinblue that is directly connected to the project website. ICLEI Europe manages the e-mail addresses and is the only responsible partner accessing Sendinblue. The newsletters contain an unsubscribe button, to ensure that personal data will be permanently deleted, when requested. Each newsletter will provide information on how to unsubscribe. Sendinblue is a GDPR compliant platform⁶, providing users the rights to request unsubscription, data cancelation, and rectification. In addition, ICLEI EURO - as responsible manager of Sendinblue - adopts a standard organisation data protection policy⁷ that will be applied to the DEFINITE-CCRI website and web portal to be developed.

3. FAIR Data

⁶ Sendinblue GDPR compliance <https://www.sendinblue.com/gdpr/>

⁷ ICLEI EURO Data Protection Policy <https://iclei-europe.org/data-protection/> accessed 14.04.2023

This Data Management Plan is implemented in order to ensure that the DEFINITE-CCRI project applies the ECs FAIR principle, whereby data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). To do so, DEFINITE-CCRI Consortium Members have agreed on establishing a series of criteria to make data available to other users.

Enabling project owners, policy makers, financiers, and other stakeholders to find and reuse the DEFINITE-CCRI research data is essential to increase the outreach of the project. Data published in DEFINITE-CCRI will be organised and stored in files and folders with appropriate metadata records to facilitate sharing and re-use. Project deliverables will be identified with a Document ID as: DEFINITE-CCRI_number of deliverable name of deliverable.

For example, this deliverable is identified as: DEFINITE-CCRI_D1.1_Data Management Plan. Other identification details for each deliverable contain details such as provided in the table 3 below:

Table 2 Deliverable table of reference

Deliverable Number	D 1.2
Deliverable Name	Data Management Plan
Full Project Title	DEFINITE-CCRI - Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
Due date of deliverable	xx.xx.2023
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Author(s)	Nuha Eltinay (ICLEI), Alina Mures (ICLEI), Alessandra Barbieri (ICLEI); Roman Mendle (ICLEI)
Reviewer(s)	Kristin Strandberg (CE), Tommaso Buso (BwB), Eleni Kanellou (NTUA), Dieter DeSmedt (COG)
Contributor(s)	All partners
WP/Task related to the deliverable	WP1/Task 1.5
Document ID	DEFINITE-CCRI_ D1.1_Data Management plan
Abstract	Short description

Files publicly available will report a reference to DEFINITE-CCRI in their description. It is recommended that the following identifier is used `DEFINITE-CCRI_(Deliverable Number)_(Deliverablename)_(date DD.MM.YYYY)_(VersionNumber).(FileType)`.

For example, `DEFINITE-CCRI_D4.2_Summary of TIP assessment reports_03032023_V1.doc`

9. Describe how we make data openly accessible

Data produced or used in DEFINITE-CCRI are shared at three levels:

- Data may be shared between consortium partners with the aim to analyse and/or prepare the project outputs, except where expressly prohibited by the terms of access to existing datasets (for secondary data) or terms of agreed informed consent to provide data (for primary data). Data are shared with project partners via access to the restricted Microsoft Teams channel. DEFINITE-CCRI may gather research data pertaining to the circular economy projects benefiting from its free services with the purpose: (1) of enhancing the understanding of their scientific components and technological aspects; (2) facilitating the customization of services, thereby easing their implementation, and increasing access to investment opportunities. Under these circumstances, the DEFINITE-CCRI project team, bound by confidentiality clauses in the Services Plan Agreements (SPAs), maintains strict confidentiality regarding the collected research data. They refrain from sharing it with third parties or publishing it publicly. Likewise, external experts engaged in service delivery may be required to sign non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) to uphold confidentiality concerning the supported circular projects.
- Data resulting from the stakeholder engagement activities, Community of practice or Capacity building webinars, and/or data from earlier research required to provide context or as a discussion point for these activities, may be shared with participants, subject to agreed terms and conditions.
- Where appropriate, data produced in DEFINITE-CCRI may be made available to the wider public as open access data shared through the project website.

Data produced in DEFINITE-CCRI will be assessed for its suitability for sharing as open access data according to criteria including:

- informed consent provided by participants (see Annex B);
- terms of access or use of data (for pre-existing datasets);

- data protection and confidentiality legislation in the states in which data has been produced and/or is stored;
- presence of personal data, and/or reasonable effort required to anonymise personal data and/or redact personal data.

Scientific publications and research data are not expected for this project, however, if any publication will result from this project, this will be made available open access and will be published on the DEFINITE-CCRI website or the EC's Open Access Publishing Platform. Data produced during the project duration will be made available, within the ethical constraints of guarantees of confidentiality and anonymity offered to stakeholders engaged.

As mentioned above, DEFINITE-CCRI will develop a website and a web portal.

- DEFINITE-CCRI website: launched in April 2023, is the primary platform to disseminate relevant project outputs and project information to a wider audience. As mentioned in the Data Management Plan, submitted in April 2023 "all relevant information and materials produced during the project's lifetime will be uploaded on the website for free consultation and download".
- DEFINITE-CCRI Deal Engine web portal (to be launched in April 2025): the portal will be hosted as sub-section of the DEFINITE-CCRI website and is designed to continue selected elements of the Deal Engine beyond the project's lifetime. It will include in particular the function to submit project outlines as well as allow users to navigate through the evaluation tool. Data produced consequently will be made available, within the ethical constraints of guarantees of confidentiality and anonymity offered to stakeholders engaged. Further features of the portal section (type of data required for PDA application, type of data accessible by stakeholders, storage system, and related features) will be further specified as necessary in the Spin-off Plan.

Several project deliverables are sensitive, for this reason they are stored on the DEFINITE-CCRI Microsoft Teams channel, accessible only to project partners; while other relevant project outputs are made accessible to the public not only via the project website, but also via other social media channels where necessary. Further information on the dissemination plan is provided in the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan completed in M6. Deliverables that are publicly disseminated are provided in the annex C, below. The dissemination level of deliverables can be Public (PU) or Sensitive (SEN).

10. Describe how we make data interoperable

Data take standard formats that can be easily operated by all consortium and project stakeholders. Publicly available software can support the project data which largely have standard data formats such as text documents (.doc, .docx, .pdf, .odt), Images (jpg, png), Audio (mp3), Video (mp4), Applications (web app, mobile app), and data stored as .xls, .xlsx or .csv files.

DEFINITE-CCRI describes project data using standard vocabularies and keywords that denote or amplify research and development work in the area of Local Circular Economy transition and Circular Innovation Financing in Europe. This facilitates interdisciplinarity and interoperability of project data and outputs for usage by stakeholders connected to the project's scope.

11. Describe how we ensure re-use of data

DEFINITE-CCRI ensures that data and outputs are interoperable and made easily reusable by interested parties and stakeholders. Products and deliverables are made available to the project consortium on the DEFINITE-CCRI Microsoft Teams channel, where all partners have access to all folders and deliverables.

Project deliverables are dedicated to proving the Deal Engine mechanism that support circular economy projects to reach bankability, therefore deliverables highlighting this process that can be publicly disseminated, are made available on the EC's Open Access Publishing Platform; on the project website; and on the portal-section of the website (once finalized); as well as on social media channels. No scientific publications are expected for the implementation of the project, therefore, only if required by project partners, such publications will be shared under a Creative Commons license (such as CC BY or CC BY-NC).

Project stakeholders and audience can request data and information on the project via the project website using the contact form that will be made available on the website. Project partners can disseminate their results in a publicly available format, unless there are restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security regulations or legitimate interests. DEFINITE-CCRI ensures that releasing or sharing data with external parties follows the rules and regulations of the Grant Agreement, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679), and other EU provisions on data sharing and protection.

DEFINITE-CCRI Consortium ensures data quality before publishing the outputs, through an internal review process engaging the overall consortium. Information disseminated via the different communication channels is curated before publication.

All publications acknowledge the receipt of funding from the Horizon Europe programme. Data deposited on the website will remain available for at least 4 years after the end of the DEFINITE-CCRI grant period.

ANNEXES

ANNEX A. Details on Datasets

Type of data	Brief description of why data is needed	Data owner	Is this data sensitive and/or personal? Yes or No (If YES, explanation provided; if NO link provided)	Primary Storage during the project (private storage)	Who has access during the project? C= consortium R=Responsible owner/custodian + project coordinator E=external parties	Backup/Security during the project R= Responsible C=Project data controller	Preserved after project (search date)? Y=All data N=No data S=Sample	Preserved format (Text, Images, Audio, Video, Excel, etc.)	Access after Project U=unrestricted R=restricted	Data volume
DEFINITE-CCRI_WP1_Project Management										
Project financial and administrative documents	Consortium agreement; Grant agreement; document amendments; Project budget; technical and financial report	Consortium	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (.html, .csv, .xlsx, .xls, .pdf)	R	4 GB
Project Deliverables	Deliverables related to the WP1 submitted to EC	Consortium	NO Published by EC via CORDIS	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	Text (.html, .csv, .xlsx, .xls, .pdf)	U	2 GB

Meeting minutes and recordings	List of participants; Updates and main points of discussion	Consortium	YES, consortium partners names and surnames	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (.html, .csv, .xlsx, .xls, .pdf)	R	12 GB
Data on consortium members and project participants	Name, surname, organization, role within the project, position, email and phone number	Consortium	YES consortium partners names and surnames	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (.html, .csv, .xlsx, .xls, .pdf)	R	1 GB
D1.3 Intellectual Property Rights Strategy	Comprehensive plan for management of IP created or processed under the project by partners and third parties.	Consortium	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	554 KB
D1.4 Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan	Plan for gender equality mainstreaming through all project activities and content to be developed for deal engine and capacity building.	Consortium	NO https://zenodo.org/records/17606714	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	1.1 MB
D1.5 Data Management Plan - Final Version	Final reviewed version of the Data Management Plan	Consortium	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607968	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	400 KB
DEFINITE-CCRI_WP2_City and Investors Engagement and Project Selection										
D2.1: Summary of DEFINITE-CCRI project pipeline on	Summarises key components of the DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline, consisting of the template and guiding questions for	ICLEI	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17606829	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	803 KB

boarding package	project outlines from engaged cities, evaluation criteria and other supporting documentation.									
D2.2: Report on proceedings of engagement with project owners	This deliverable summarises the meeting and engagement proceedings as well as the status quo of projects prepared by cities and associated data and other information available.	ICLEI	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	Word	R	400 KB
D2.3: Report on Investor Base and Financial Instruments	This deliverable summarises the investors and their financial instruments as a basis of the work carried out under WP3 & WP5.	BwB	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17606864	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	623 KB
D2.4: Letters of Intent signed by at least (5) investors	This deliverable will outline contents of at least 5 MoU signed between the DEFINITE-CCRI project partners and investors (financial institutions) once initial screening of projects is complete. The list of signed agreements will be expanded to 10 by the end of the project	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Word, PDF	R	400 KB
D2.5: Shortlist of projects receiving PDA support	The deliverable summarises the (4) projects selected during the pre-selection phase to receive PDA support under the Deal Engine process.	ICLEI	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17606985	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	895 KB
DEFINITE-CCRI_ WP3_Financial and Legal Project Development Assistance										

Additional data on project outlines	Other technical and financial data, to be decided based on proceedings with cities and data needed for the Technical Impact Potential assessment and Financial Investment Baseline assessment.	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Word, Excel	R	22.9 MB
Meetings notes and pictures	Main points of discussion, updates and information on projects. Such deliverable includes sensitive information.	Consortium	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	S	Word, Excel, images	R	
D3.1: Report on methodology for the FIB and financial due-diligence	This deliverable reports on the financial and legal assessment related components of the DEFINITE-CCRI methodology related to financial and legal assessment, covering methodology, assessment criteria, guidance document, excel sheets etc.	BwB	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607054	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	932 KB
D3.2: Summary of FIB risk analysis reports	This deliverable provides a summary of the (4) individual FIB reports prepared for each proposal.	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	PDF, Word	R	20 MB
Data for financial due diligence compliance	Data needed to prepare risk profiles for projects for financial appraisal. Type of data needed will be defined once the due diligence process.	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (.html, .csv, .xlsx, .xls, .pdf)	R	5 MB

			business information							
D3.3: Report on financial due diligence proceedings	This report documents the support proceedings and results of the financial due diligence phase and summarises final project risk profiles.	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive business informatio	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	PDF, Word	R	10 MB
DEFINITE-CCRI_WP4_ Technological Project Development Assistance										
Additional data on project outlines	Other technical and financial data, to be decided based on proceedings with cities and data needed for the Technical Impact Potential assessment and Financial Investment Baseline assessment.	NTUA	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Word, Excel	R	1 MB
Meetings notes and pictures	Main points of discussion, updates and information on projects. Such deliverable includes sensitive information.	Consortium	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	S	Word, Excel, images	R	500 MB
D4.1: Report on methodology for the TIP and technical due-diligence	This deliverable reports on the technological and impact assessment related components of the CCRI Deal Brokerage methodology, covering the methodology, assessment criteria, guidance document, excel sheets, etc.	NTUA	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607480	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	1.7 MB
D4.2: Summary of TIP	This report provides a summary of the individual TIP reports prepared for each project outline.	NTUA	YES Personnel data, sensitive	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	PDF, Word	R	10 MB

assessment reports			business information							
Data for financial due diligence compliance	Data needed to prepare risk profiles for projects for financial appraisal. Type of data needed will be defined once the due diligence process.	NTUA	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (.html, .csv, .xlsx, .xls, .pdf)	R	7.5 GB
D4.3: Report on technical due diligence proceedings	This report documents the support proceedings and results of the technical due diligence phase and summarises project profiles for appraisal.	NTUA	YES Personnel data, sensitive business informatio	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	PDF, Word	R	10 MB
Conference paper - Assessing the Impact of Circular Economy Projects: The DEFINITE-CCRI Approach	This paper presents the technical and impact potential assessment provided for selected circular economy projects by DEFINITE-CCRI.	NTUA	NO https://zenodo.org/records/17598192	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	453.1 KB
Conference paper - Charting the impact of circular economy projects: the DEFINITE-CCRI approach	This paper presents the technical and impact potential assessment provided for selected circular economy projects by DEFINITE-CCRI. Building on teh conference paper "Assessing the Impact of Circular Economy Projects: The DEFINITE-CCRI Approach", this paper delves into how the	NTUA	NO https://zenodo.org/records/17598283	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	157.7 KB

	approach was operationalized in the project.									
DEFINITE-CCRI_WP5_ Project Bankability Appraisal and Deal Brokerage										
D5.1: Report on Project Appraisal Event and Final Conference WP5	Report on partially public, physical event including closed-door appraisal sessions for projects supported by DEFINITECCRI with investors.	ICLEI	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	S	Word, PDF	U	3.5 MB
D5.2: Report on Project Appraisal Proceedings	The report on project appraisal proceedings summarizes the organization, implementation and outcomes of the Appraisal Event.	BwB	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607583	Zenodo	C,R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	4.2 MB
D5.3: Bankable project profiles and business plans ready for investment	Report which summarises and describes all four projects reaching the stage of investor sign-off, including focus and scope, business plans, process of “how and why they got there”, as well as the investors’ rationale for financing them.	BwB	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607604	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	4.1 MB
D5.3: Bankable project profiles and businessplans ready for investment	Report which summarises and describes all four projects reaching the stage of investor sign-off, including focus and scope, business plans, process of “how and why they got there”, as well as the investors’	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R,	R	Y	PDF, Word	R	100 MB

	rationale for financing them. This restricted version, has been developed for consortium, projects supported and the EC and includes additional technical and financial information and details on the projects.									
D5.4: Report on proceedings of contract preparation	Confidential report that outlines the proceedings of the contract facilitation workshop and contract preparation proceedings of funded projects.	BwB	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R,	R	Y	PDF, Word	R	50 MB
D5.5: Project evaluation tool and guidebook	This deliverable is a guidebook on the project evaluation tool, aimed at providing guidance to users on how to use the tool via the web portal.	BwB	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF	U	20 MB
Circularity Tool	The DEFINTIE-CCRI Circularity Tool will help you develop your circular venture. The tool has two Modules and each Module has two Units.	ICLEI	NO https://tool.definite-ccri.eu/	Project website: https://tool.definite-ccri.eu/	C, R, E	R	Y	Online Tool	U	23.4 MB
DEFINITE-CCRI_WP6_Communication, Replication and Exploitation										
Website content	General project information	ICLEI	NO https://definite-ccri.eu/	MS Teams, project website: https://definite-ccri.eu/	C, R, E	R	Y	Text (txt., doc., docx., pdf, .html) Images (png, jpeg)	U	270 MB

Project Newsletter via Sendinblue	Name and Surname, e-mail address of subscribers	ICLEI	YES Personnel data	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (txt., doc., docx., pdf, .html), Images (png, jpeg), EML	R	10 MB
Posters, flyers	General project information	Consortium	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C,R, E	R	Y	(.jpg, .jpeg, .gif, .png, .svg, .psd)	U	50 MB
Presentations	Project information	Consortium	NO https://definite-ccri.eu/	Website: https://definite-ccri.eu/	C, R	R	N	Text, doc., docx., pdf,), Images (png, jpeg), EML	U	50 MB
D6.1: Communications Toolkit	Visual identity, promotion material, social media accounts and document templates for partner use.	CE	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	PDF	U	17.6 MB
D6.3: Capacity building materials	DEFINITE-CCRI brings together high-impact circularity projects and funding institutions to boost the transition to a circular economy. This channel hosts educational videos designed to help European cities and	CE	NO Youtube link: https://www.youtube.com/@DEFINITE-CCRI	Youtube; MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	mp4	U	12.6 GB

	regions develop bankable circular economy projects.									
D6.4: Report on video production proceedings	This report outlines the proceedings and results of the 20 educational videos produced and launched.	CoG	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF, Word	U	200 KB
D6.5: Report on CoP	This report summarises proceedings and results of Community of Practice setup and creation, members and their interactions to describe the successful creation of a community of practice and it's status to date. A final iteration of the report will be finalized in M28 and include proceedings of meetings and collaborations created via the CoP throughout the project	CE	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF, Word	U	10 MB
D6.6: Project spin-off plan	This report outlines the co-developed plan for a DEFINITE-CCRI spin-off that continues to provide related financing and PDA services and builds on the project's results.	CE	YES Personnel data, sensitive business information	MS Teams	C, R	R	Y	Text (txt., doc., docx., pdf, .html), Images (png, jpeg), EML	R	450 KB
D6.7 Dissemination, Communication and	Plan for all DisComEx activities outlined in section 2.2 and include a regularly updated tracker to measure and verify KPIs.	ICLEI	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF, Word	U	1 MB

Exploitation Plan - Initial Version			to consortium)							
D6.8 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan - Final Version	Plan for all DisComEx activities outlined in section 2.2 and include a regularly updated tracker to measure and verify KPIs.	ICLEI	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607918	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF, Word	U	1.4 MB
D6.9 Policy Brief 1	First policy brief summarising the preliminary lessons learned from engaging with investors and project owners, drawing from D2.2 and D2.3 for publication on the web portal, and providing recommendations for policy makers on how to better facilitate access to investment for local and regional circular economy projects.	ICLEI	NO (no public interest, can be accessed upon request to consortium)	MS Teams	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF, Word	U	500 KB
D6.10 Policy Brief 2	Final policy brief summarizing final lessons learned from implementing the deal engine, including barriers for project development assistance for publication on the web portal, and providing recommendations for policy makers on how to better facilitate access to investment for local and	ICLEI	NO https://zenodo.org/uploads/17607937	Zenodo	C, R, E	R	Y	PDF, Word	U	842 KB

**Definite
CCRI**

	regional circular economy projects.									
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ANNEX B. DEFINITE-CCRI Consent Form

This Declaration of Informed Consent consists of two parts. In the first part, Part A, your signed consent is requested. You will have the opportunity to withdraw from DEFINITE-CCRI, at any moment without any consequences.

In the second part Part B, information regarding the project and terms of your requested participation is provided.

PART A

With my signature, I, _____ (stakeholder participant), confirm the following:

1. I have been given sufficient information about this research project. The purpose of my participation in this project has been explained to me and is clear.
2. I have been made aware by the researcher/staff, _____, that my participation is entirely voluntary. There is no explicit or implicit coercion whatsoever to participate.
3. I have been made aware by the researcher/staff that I can terminate my participation at any time.
4. I have been given the explicit guarantees that the project staff will securely store the data and information provided.
5. This consent form is valid for all DEFINITE-CCRI activities in which I will take part. Furthermore, regarding the handling of my personal data (please check one):
 - I agree to the processing of my personal data.
 - I declare that the researcher/staff may identify me by name or function in reports or publications in which information obtained from me is used.

Participant's Signature, Date

Researcher's Signature, Date

Researcher's Contact Details

INFORMATION (PART B)

1. Voluntary participation

You as a stakeholder will always participate in the sessions on a voluntary basis. Before the start of each session, you will be asked to sign this Informed Consent Declaration document.

You will have the opportunity to withdraw from the research at any moment without any consequences.

2. Personal data protection and privacy

Your rights to privacy and protection of personal data will be respected at all time. You will be given full justification in case of collection and/or processing of your personal sensitive data. Procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction will comply with all national and EU-legislation, and are set out in the project's Data Management Plan. Any use of personal data will be strictly limited to the scope, duration and aim of the project. Any exceptions to this will require your explicit consent.

3. Information about the results of the project

The final results of the project will be disseminated, published and made available to the public.

4. Contact

In case you have any questions at any time, please contact:

[Insert full name].....

[insert email and/or phone number].....

ANNEX C. List of deliverables and dissemination level

Del	Name	Partner	Due (M)	Dissemination level
D1.1	Project Management Plan and Tracker	ICLEI	3	PU
D1.2	Data Management Plan Initial Version	ICLEI	6	PU
D1.3	Intellectual Property Rights Strategy	ICLEI	6	PU
D1.4	Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan	ICLEI	3	PU
D1.5	The final version of the Data Management Plan	ICLEI	28	PU
D2.1	Summary of project DEFINITE-CCRI project pipeline on-boarding package	ICLEI	6	PU
D2.3	Report on Investor Base and Financial Instruments	BWB	8	PU
D2.5	Shortlist of projects receiving PDA support	ICLEI	10	PU
D3.1	Report on methodology for the FIB and financial due-diligence	BWB	10	PU
D4.1	Report on methodology for the TIP and technical due-diligence	NTUA	10	PU
D5.1	Report on Project Appraisal Event and Final Conference	ICLEI	24	PU
D5.2	Report on Project Appraisal Proceedings	BWB	26	PU
D5.3	Bankable project profiles and business plans ready for investment	BWB	26	PU
D5.5	Project evaluation tool and guidebook	BWB	24	PU
D6.1	Communications Toolkit	CE	4	PU
D6.2	DEFINITE-CCRI web portal	ICLEI	6	PU
D6.3	Capacity building materials	CE	24	PU
D6.4	Report on capacity building webinars	CoG	30	PU

D6.5	Report on Community of Practice (CoP)	CoG	12	PU
D6.7	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan Initial version	ICLEI	6	PU
D6.8	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan Final version	ICLEI	28	PU
D6.9	Policy Brief 1	ICLEI	12	PU
D6.10	Policy Brief 2	ICLEI	30	PU

**Definite
CCRI**

contact@definite-ccri.eu

**Circular
Cities & Regions
Initiative**
CCRI Project

*An initiative
of the*

www.definite-ccri.eu